

From a TOMS to a Digital Twin

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Training Operations and Maintenance Simulator (TOMS) are very precise and complete satellite simulators whereon runs the On Board SoftWare (OBSW). These simulators model most avionic units as well as the physical environment. However, TOMS are not entirely representative, especially due to the degradation and wear of satellite components over time. Increasing the representativeness of a TOMS can already improve the operational work performed with it. Maintaining such a high representativeness over time would allow to go a step further by turning the TOMS into a powerful tool for predictive maintenance. With this goal in mind, we propose an approach to turn a TOMS into a Digital Twin following two approaches further incorporating AI techniques. These approaches are namely, reconfiguration and surrogate modelling. Herein, we demonstrate a Proof of Concept (PoC) by applying these two approaches on different subsystems of a satellite and corroborate their viability. Additionally, we compare the performance of different AI techniques using these two distinct approaches for the PoC.

1 Introduction

Training Operations and Maintenance Simulator (TOMS) are satellite simulators that usually simulate all components of the satellite from the platform to the payload as well as the physical environment. The physical environment includes the computation of forces and torques applied on the satellite either through the space environment (atmospheric drag, solar radiation pressure, etc...) or produced by actuators (reaction wheels, propulsion, etc...). The actual On Board SoftWare (OBSW) running on the satellite is executed on such simulation, usually using emulation technology. This makes the TOMS a very representative simulation as the OBSW runs as it does on the real satellite. Such simulations are thus used to test oper-

ational procedures, to investigate potential problems or to test the deployment of an updated OBSW before loading it on the real satellite. However, the representativeness of a TOMS is not perfect and further degrades over-time due to wear of satellite components. The purpose of this work is to use AI techniques to improve the representativeness of the TOMS as well as to maintain such representativeness over time. We consider the synchronization aspect between the real satellite and the simulation a key aspect to build a Digital Twin (DT). In this work, we define our DT as an evolved simulation that runs in parallel to the real satellite (physical twin) such that it can automatically reconfigure to follow any evolution of the satellite (for more generic definition of DT, see [1] and [2]). The approach followed in this work differs from other similar DT development (e.g., [3], [4] or [5]). Whereas most DT's tend to overly simplify the problem to optimise their predictive results and showcase the best potential algorithms, this work starts from the real and complex situation, and attempts to build an effective solution given the practical limitations. With this goal in mind, we propose an approach to turn a TOMS into a Digital Twin. Two complementary approaches are studied. The first one is the reconfiguration (or recalibration) of the simulation to ensure that the representativeness is maintained over time. The second is called surrogate modelling. It uses real telemetries (TM) received by the satellite to learn a given behavior that is not well simulated by the TOMS. A predictive model trained on the TM is then inserted in the simulation to increase its representativeness on a specific aspect. These two approaches are further described below. In order to validate these approaches two PoC are realised. They are based on the SWOT satellite launched in December 2022. The SWOT TOMS is thus used and the real TM are gathered from the SWOT operation center at CNES.

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2 Reconfiguration

We started the transformation of a TOMS towards a DT following the reconfiguration approach. For this, we first ensure that the TOMS is maintained in the same state as the real satellite by feeding it with the same telecommands (TC) as the ones sent to the real satellite. We then compare the telemetries (TM) received from the real satellite and the ones generated from the TOMS. By comparing them using an AI algorithm, we infer the differences between the simulation and the real satellite. The simulation is then automatically updated based on the identified differences in order to maintain its representativeness. This transformation is performed following several steps. First of all, the simulation needs to be upgraded in order to offer the possibility of re-configuration. For example, if an increased friction of the reaction wheel is detected, the simulation has to offer the possibility to adjust this effect for the update to be done. In addition, representativeness of the simulation might need to be improved on specific aspects in order to properly spot the satellite physical evolution with the telemetry comparison. One important part of this transformation chain is the development of a data pipeline which is developed to transform the raw telemetries to a set of data digestible by an AI algorithm. The AI system formed of the AI algorithm itself as well as the data processing part is constrained by several aspects. First, representative data should be generated in advance in order to execute the algorithm (with lazy learners) or train the model (with active learners) as fast as possible when TMs from the satellite are available. Then, it should be able to deal with different types of variables. In the TM the data can be categorical, integers or floating points values (for more information about TM data and AI, see [6]). In addition, one variable can affect multiple parameters in the TM. At the same time, multiple separated parameters can affect the same variable. The process selected for the training of the AI system is the following. First a set of possible ranges for physical parameter variations is selected. For example, a range for the acceptable reaction wheel friction is defined. Then simulation runs are executed with parameters variations within their own defined range. From these simulation runs, the relevant TM parameters are collected. The TM parameters tagged with the simulation parameter values used to generate them are then fed to the AI system for pre-processing and training. This allows the AI system to learn the link between the TM and the simulation parameters. Testing of the AI system and the pipeline is performed by holding one set of parameters and generated TM from the training, and ensuring that the AI system is

able to predict the value of those parameters from the corresponding TM. Once the AI system is trained, it is fed with real data from the physical twin and is asked to predict simulation parameters. The simulation is then updated by changing its parameters. This can be done while the simulation is running keeping the synchronisation state between the digital twin and the physical twin. Several challenges are faced in the development of the described approach. The main one is the execution speed of the TOMS. These simulators usually do not run much faster than real time. Using them to generate the data in large quantity can prove difficult. It might thus be required to split the TOMS in sub-components in order to generate training and testing data. Another challenge comes from the OBSW and the fact that the system is in a close loop. For an AI algorithm, learning to associate a set of simulation parameters to an effect in the output TM is already difficult. Depending on the situation, the OBSW might have a transformation or filtering effect on the data (e.g., TM content can change as a function of the satellite mode). This complicates even further the learning of the link between the simulation parameter vs TM evolution. This also implies that a re-training might be required upon OBSW update.

3 Orbital drift

As a proof of concept (PoC), we apply the above approach to a sub-component of the TOMS. The actual orbit of the satellite can vary w.r.t. the simulated one. Many effects can cause this but we focus on the atmospheric friction and the radiation pressure. The purpose of the PoC is to compare PVT (Position/Velocity/Time) information found in telemetries between the physical and digital twin and infer the required simulation parametrization to better fit the actual observed orbit. This first PoC focusing on the orbit aims to start with a well understood physical aspect. The physical laws impacting the orbit are well known and the actual orbit of a satellite is finely reconstructed on the ground. This allows to fully validate the behavior and the various output of the DT. For this use case, the identified parameters in the simulation are the friction coefficients of the satellite, the atmospheric density and the solar flux experienced by the satellite (FAS). These parameters are chosen because they have a significant impact on the actual orbit of the satellite. Atmospheric density is computed from an atmospheric model and varies at each step of the simulation. Solar flux is based on predictions and distance from the Sun. In the simulation these parameters are adjusted by variables that the AI algorithm is trained to predict. The purpose of the DT is to learn to

modify these parameters in order to better fit reality.

In more details, several evolution of the orbit (PVT data) are generated using the simulation by varying the 3 variables that the AI is meant to predict (FAS). This allows for the AI to learn the link between the simulation variables and the evolution of the PVT. Once the AI model is trained, it is inserted within the simulation such that at a configurable frequency, it can be fed with real PVT data (measured from the real satellite) and can predict values for the three variables (thus impacting the calculation of atmospheric drag and solar pressure). The simulation orbit is then reset to the real (measured) one and the simulation (the DT) continues to predict the orbit with the updated variable to better represent reality and thus better predict the orbit evolution.

Two AI approaches have been tested and their performance compared. The first one is Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) [7] using a modified Dapper implementation [8]. In this approach [9], we augment the state vector containing the PVT of the orbit with the parameters (FAS) that generated that orbit. When assimilating the observation containing only the PVT, we get an estimate for the corresponding parameters FAS. We use that estimation as the correction to be applied to the model. The second one is a Two Dimension Convolutional Neural Network (2D-CNN)[10]. There, the algorithm consumes the PVT as input, and is trained to predict the FAS as output, to be used as correction.

4 Surrogate modelling for thermal aspects

The idea of this second approach is to build a surrogate model for the heater consumption. Indeed, the heaters are controlled by the OBSW as a function of the temperature sensors. However, the thermal aspects are not (or lightly) simulated in a TOMS. This leads to a non-representative drive of the heaters and thus a non-representative current consumption and battery state of charge. This PoC is more complex than the previous one as the thermal aspects require dedicated resource consuming computations to be simulated. We thus directly use real data to build our surrogate model. These real data for heater consumption are shown in Figure 1. In order to improve the representativeness of the simulation w.r.t. current consumption, an AI algorithm will be trained with real TM to predict the current consumption at each step in the simulation. The first task is to select the appropriate data set that will allow to extract the link between the position of the satellite on its orbit and its environ-

Figure 1: Sum of heater consumption as a function of time (one month of data). Exact values of consumption and date do not appear.

ment on one side, and the current consumption of the heaters on the other side. It is unknown if giving raw data (attitude quaternion, position, date, etc) directly extracted from the TM is enough or if data should be pre-processed (eclipse state, direction of the Sun w.r.t. solar arrays, ...). The two sets of data are used to train a model separately in order to compare the results. This hinges on whether it is necessary to involve an expert in the process or not. For the purpose of the surrogate modelling, a neural network model has been selected. Using two months of real TM data, we target a prediction precision of a week. Using more data would allow to predict further in time.

Problem Formalization Since we aim at forecasting the total power consumption of the heaters and that we receive this information in the TM, the problem at hand is basically a Time Series Forecasting problem. Given:

- a univariate time series $C = (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_T)$ where c_t is a variable representing the heater consumption at time step t ,
- a multivariate time series dataset $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T)$, where $x_t = (x_{t,1}, x_{t,2}, \dots, x_{t,N})$ is a vector of N variables at time step t ,

the goal is to predict values of the time series C for H times steps ahead, i.e, we want to predict $C = (c_{T+1}, c_{T+1}, \dots, c_{T+H})$.

The forecasting problem can be formulated as a supervised learning task, where we aim to learn a function f that maps the past observations to the future values:

$$\hat{c}_{T+h} = f(c_T, c_{T-1}, \dots, c_{T-M+1}, x_T, x_{T-1}, \dots, x_{T-M+1})$$

where \hat{c}_{T+h} is the predicted value at time step $T + h$ and M is the number of past time steps used as input to the model. For our use case, the dataset X will respectively be called X_{raw} and $X_{\text{pre-processed}}$ if we use raw data or pre-processed data.

Considered approaches Several approaches have been used to solve the Time Series Forecasting problem in general. One that stands out is Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) [11]. This statistical model assumes that the time series data is a linear function of past values and random errors which may not hold for all types of data. Another drawback is that model parameters can be difficult to set. While ARIMA has been a default method for a long time, time series forecasting is not immune to the recent success enabled by advanced deep learning approaches. While many exist [12–16], their performance will depend on the amount and quality of the data. For our use case, we implemented a 1 Dimension Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN) [17]. Its architecture is fairly simple: we have 3 convolutional layers of a convolution stride of 1 and a kernel size of 3. The size of their output channels are 64, 128, and 64 respectively. We then use 2 fully connected layers outputting 128 and H neurons respectively.

We use ARIMA as a baseline approach, and compare it to our 1D-CNN architecture. Note that we do not use the exogeneous variables X in the case of ARIMA as it would require the model to be fit to also predict future exogeneous variables values.

In the end, the surrogate model obtained will be included in the simulation in order to conclude this PoC. A way forward to further increase the complexity of a follow up use case would be to build a surrogate model for the various temperature sensors of the satellite. This would then let the OBSW directly drive the heaters for an even improved representativeness.

5 Results

Reconfiguration The realization of the PoC allowed to build the data pipeline required to gather the TM, extract calibrated parameters and export these parameters to a format suitable to be used for the training of an AI algorithm. As the various parameters were extracted and available in a csv format, a simple tool allowed to compare the list of TM parameters over time to assess the representativeness of the TOMS on each sub-components of the satellite. Comparing the two followed AI approaches, EnKF are extremely robust, as they always provide estimations sampled from the available ensemble, even when the observations are outside the ensemble's distribution. They do tend to

handle low data availability quite well, and are well suited for this application, due to the difficulty of producing a lot of data. Finally, they do not require training in advance, which reduces the computational cost significantly. However, the prediction time compared to a trained AI model is significantly longer (few seconds vs few minutes). On the other hand, the 2D-CNN is much more sensitive to the quality of the data. Any missing or unexpected values will have a large impact on the model, as well as outliers, leading to wrong or no predictions at all. However, it offers the advantage of being trainable beforehand, and the model can be saved for further predictions unlike the EnKF. The chosen approach is then to use the 2D-CNN to the real TM and if it fails, then the EnKF can be used to ensure a prediction. The predicted parameters are then automatically used to update the simulation. First the PoC has been tested on simulated data on which the solar flux and the atmospheric density had been changed w.r.t. the parameters usually used in the TOMS. The PoC managed to find the new values with an error¹ of $\sim 7\%$ and $\sim 10\%$ for EnKF and 2D-CNN, respectively. With more data available, it expected for the 2D-CNN to become more precise than EnKF.

The PoC was then deployed at the operation center of the SWOT satellite at the CNES facilities. It was fed with real TM and the simulation parameters were automatically updated within the simulation proving the reconfiguration approach.

Surrogate Modelling While this will need to be confirmed by the ongoing study, Figure 2 provides some preliminary results. Out of one month of the available data, we kept the last 15% as a test set and we evaluate the prediction of 24 hours of future consumptions with a 5 minutes precision. Given the limited amount of data, that was done only from one up to four days ahead. Predictions is also based on 24 hours of data with a 5 minutes precision. As expected ARIMA performs worse, and prediction performance decreases as we predict further in time. Pre-processed features seem to slightly improve performance but not significantly.

As a next step, the surrogate model will be included in the TOMS and the battery state of charge between the DT and the real satellite will be compared. This will allow to conclude on the improvement of the TOMS thanks to the surrogate modelling.

¹Mean Squared Error over normalized validation set.

Figure 2: Forecasting Mean Absolute Error on Test Set

6 Discussion

The reconfiguration PoC presented in this work focused on a specific aspect and considered 3 parameters. In a more complex case in which the DT is kept synchronised with the physical satellite on a broad range of components from the power system to the thermal management, a significant evolution of the TOMS is required. Indeed, the more systems are considered in the DT, the more interactions between the various TM parameters need to be understood by the AI algorithm and thus need to be simulated. However, such high representative simulation especially if they run the OBSW can show terrible performances and it might be impossible to generate enough data using the entire TOMS.

It seems more feasible to divide the TOMS into several sub-components, both for data generation as well as for AI algorithm selection and training because model selection will depend on the type of data and their evolutions. The proper division in sub-components and the combination of the many outputs of the various models used remains to be done based on specific expertise and might be different for different satellites.

Since the surrogate modelling approach is based on time series, the developed method should be applicable to any other TM parameter and the approach is not limited to thermal aspects. It could be power consumption of specific equipment for example.

In the case of predictive maintenance, it is essential to model wear in the simulation and to design in advance the various parameters that can be used to model this wear. In addition, although comparing the real TM with the output of the TOMS is easy because these data come in the same format, the frequency at which data are available in TM can be limiting. It is especially the case for phenomena that happen at

high frequencies (e.g., use of thrusters and manoeuvre).

The possibility to turn a TOMS into a DT is thus limited by the amount of information available in the TM as well as by its execution speed that will need to be improved in the future in order to perform predictive maintenance.

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